

Development of numerical model for the complex permittivity of the carbon nanocomposites at microwave frequency band

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SUMMARY

In this paper, we have studied on the numerical model for the complex permittivity of carbon nanocomposites in microwave frequency band based on the percolation theory. The model was built up for complex permittivity of E-glass fabric/epoxy composite laminates containing carbon black (CB), carbon nanofiber (CNF) at the frequency band of 0.5 GHz ~ 18.0 GHz. It is composed of the numerical equations of the scaling law used in percolation theory and constants obtained from experiments to quantify the model. The model describes the complex permittivity as the function of frequency and filler concentration. The model was verified by being compared with the measurements.

Keywords: carbon, nanocomposite, complex permittivity, percolation, numerical model

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric matrix composites are being widely used in the electrical application field by means of controlling their electric property by replacing some parts of their polymeric structure with functional elements or by adding other conductive fillers. Nowadays, carbon nano materials such as carbon black, carbon nanofiber, carbon nanotube, graphene, etc are appearing to be representatives for the conductive fillers because of their high electric conductivity and their inherent light density.

Conductive polymeric composites can be applied in many different kinds of specific application area according to the electric conductivity. One of well established area is antistatic application. The electric conductivity for this application is about 10^{-5} S/m. Recently, Highly loaded composites are being studied to be used in the bi-polar plates or electric cathodes. The electric conductivity for this application is over than 10^3 S/m, much higher than the previous application.

Radar absorbing composite technology can be included in the application area of low conductivity materials of about 10^{-5} ~ 1 S/m. Recently, many studies on E-glass fibre-reinforced polymer matrix composites were reported to utilize their high structural performance as well as the capability to become radar absorbing materials (RAM) by adding the conductive fillers into the polymer matrix [1]. It is due to the merits both in manufacturing process and in application performance. In the manufacturing process,

the epoxy resin for the composite prepreg can be diluted with acetone to get low viscosity in order to have much higher concentration of carbon nano materials. The acetone can be easily evaporated in the drying process of the prepreg. Even more, the fibre-reinforcement can stop the possible sinkage of agglomeration of the carbon nano materials, which make the property gradient in the composite materials. In application performance, the E-glass fibre-reinforced nanocomposite for the radar absorbing composite material (RACM) has to be used in the exterior of the structure to be exposed in aerodynamic stress, humidity or any other atmospheric environment and sometimes has to be used as structural material itself.

The electric property of nanocomposites is related to the current of free electrons in conductive fillers dispersed in the composites. Especially, in the microwave frequency band for the military or civil radar, the dielectric constant, as well as the conductivity, has to be considered [1, 2].

The electric current in the nanocomposites can be changed according to the effective length that the electrons can move in a phase of AC electric field and network structure foamed by the conductive filler dispersed in the nanocomposites. This change is the reason why the electric property of the nanocomposites is the function of the frequency and filler concentration. The theoretical understanding on this electrical property and the numerical model based on this physical theory, percolation theory, can be good tools for enlarging the application region of carbon nanocomposites. In this paper, E-glass fabric/epoxy composite laminates containing carbon black (CB), carbon nanofiber (CNF) were fabricated and the numerical model for the electric property of the carbon nanocomposite was studied.

THEORIES

Electrical Conductivity

Conduction of polymeric materials mixed with conductive nano fillers is induced by the strong electric field effect between the conductive particles or by the movement of electrons through direct contact of particles. In the former case, processes such as tunneling, field emission, and space charge limited transport should be considered; whereas, in the latter case, resistive (ohmic) relation between the current and voltage generated through a consistent conductive network formed by the direct contact between carbon nano materials should be considered. Thus, because of these various phenomena mentioned earlier, it is apparent that the mathematical models describing the properties of electro-conductive composite materials tend to be very complicated [2].

The dielectric constant and ac conductivity of a composite material are related to anomalous diffusion within each cluster and the depolarization effect between the clusters composed of conductive fillers inside the composite. These phenomena also cause the dielectric constant and electric conductivity of a composite material to become a function of all frequencies [2]. The following are three different factors to determine the dielectric constant and conductivity of a composite material:

1. Material characteristics of each component of the composite.

2. Spatial dispersion form of components within the composite.
3. Surface resistant characteristics between conductive powders.

From a microscopic point of view, we can analogize that the manufacturing process, as well as the conductivity of fillers, can have influence on the electric property of the composites, for manufacturing process effects the dispersion of fillers and the structural shape [2, 3, 4].

Percolation theory for DC electric field

In the percolation theory, the conductive fillers build conductive clusters. Each of the clusters is a group in which all the members of conductive elements are electrically connected. When the concentration is very low and fillers are well dispersed, the clusters are isolated to each other. In this situation, the electric conductivity of composite is very low. But, as the concentration get higher, the clusters meet each other and make infinite cluster(s) which is connected from one side to the other side of the composite, making the electric circuit(s) for electric current in DC electric field. So, the electric conductivity of the composites jumps at the critical concentration, so called percolation threshold, of the conductive filler. Equation (1) is for the DC electric property for the conductive filler concentration above percolation threshold.

$$\sigma_{DC} \propto (p - p_c)^t \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), p , p_c are concentration of the filler and critical concentration respectively [5].

Percolation theory for AC electric field

The electric property of nanocomposites in AC electric field can be expressed with the complex permittivity ($\varepsilon_r = \varepsilon_r' - j\varepsilon_r'' = \varepsilon' / \varepsilon_0 - j\sigma / 2\pi f \varepsilon_0$), in which real part is dielectric constant and the imaginary part is lossy term caused by ohmic resistance [3].

The distance that the electron in a cluster can move in a phase of AC current is called to be *electron displacement scale*, $L(\omega)$, which is inversely proportional to the frequency of the electric field. If a cluster in a composite is so smaller than $L(\omega)$ that the electrons in the cluster move in short time and stay on one side of the cluster in most of the duration of a phase, the cluster acts as an electric dipole. If a cluster is so larger than $L(\omega)$ that the electrons in the cluster are moving in all the duration of a phase, the cluster acts as an electric circuit. It means that, when the frequency of the AC electric field goes up, $L(\omega)$ get shorter and the electric circuit portion of the all clusters increases. On the contrary, when the frequency goes up, the electric dipole portion of the clusters decreases. So, we can expect that the AC conductivity of the composite is directly proportional and the dielectric constant is inversely proportional to the frequency.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing for the clusters which act as a dipole and an electric circuit.

In the percolation theory, the electric property in AC electric field is also related to *the correlation length (connectivity length) ζ* of the clusters, Equation (2), which is similar to the mean size of all the clusters excluding the infinite cluster.

$$\zeta = \zeta_0 |p - p_c|^{-\nu} \quad (2)$$

If $p > p_c$ and $L(\omega) > \zeta$, $L(\omega)$ is no longer function of ω . We can adopt new variable of *effective length scale L_ζ* as below,

$$L_\zeta \sim \begin{cases} L(\omega) \sim \omega^{-1/(2+\theta)}, & L(\omega) < \zeta \\ \zeta \sim |p - p_c|^{-\nu}, & L(\omega) > \zeta \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The constants of t , ν , θ are from the theoretical definition of the cluster in percolation theory. In the equation (3), we can say that, if $p > p_c$ and $L(\omega) > \zeta$, the electric conductivity is only dependent on p , not ω . In the microwave frequency band of $p \approx p_c$ and $L(\omega) < \zeta$, the electric conductivity σ' and dielectric constant ε' can be expressed as below,

$$\sigma'(p, f) \propto f^x \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon'(p, f) \propto f^{-y} \quad (5)$$

The exponent x and y have *universal relationship* of $x + y \approx 1$.

Numerical model for complex permittivity in AC electric field

In the papers of Kim, et al. [1], Laibowitz, et al. [6] and Conner, et al. [7], we can deduct the equations for the electrical property in the microwave frequency band of $p > p_c$ and $L(\omega) < \zeta$ as below,

$$\sigma'(p, f) = K_1 f^x + K_2 \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon'_r(p, f) = K_3 f^{-y} + K_4 \quad (7)$$

The exponents x , y ($1 > x, y > 0$, $x + y \approx 1$) reflect the influence of decrease of the effective distance of electron movement in accordance to the frequency f in AC electric field. The K_i components can be defined to be equations of $K_i = a_i(p - p_c)^{b_i} + c_i$, where $i=1\sim 4$, which reflect the increasing number of conductive clusters in the composites in proportion to the concentration p of conductive fillers.

The formations of equations (6), (7) for the numerical model are from the percolation theory. In the equations, the exponents x , y are dependent on the configuration of cluster, so that they are dependent on the shape of conductive fillers. The constants a_i , b_i , c_i and p_c are dependent on the material system and manufacturing process.

EXPERIMENTS

Fabrication

The laminates were fabricated with the E-glass fabric/epoxy prepregs and cured in an autoclave. The dispersions for the prepregs were made by stirring the mixture of the ultra low viscous epoxy blending diluted by acetone and the carbon nano material with the high speed mechanical stirrer and coated onto #110 E-glass fabric (nominal thickness = 0.111 mm) of HANKOOK fiber glass Co., Ltd. Table 1 shows the dimension of the CB (HG-1P of LINZI HUAGUANG Chemical Ind. in China) and CNF (PYROGRAF III APPLIED SCIENCE Inc. in USA). Figure 2 shows the fabrication procedure of the composite laminates. Table 2 shows weight contents (wt%) w of carbon nano materials in the epoxy resin of the composite laminates. The resin volume fractions v_r of the laminates are about 40%.

Table 1. Configuration of carbon nano materials.

Material Code	Material Name	Size (Diameter)	Length
CB	Carbon Black	0.3 μm (0.025 μm powder) ^a	–
CNF	Carbon Nanofiber	0.15 μm ^a	10 – 30 μm ^a

^a Values are obtained from the manufacturers' specifications.

Figure 2. Manufacturing process for E-glass fabric/epoxy composite laminates containing carbon nano materials.

Figure 3 shows the carbon nano materials and the cross sectional configurations of the composite laminates containing 2 wt% of carbon nano materials. The composite laminates consist of reinforcing fiber and epoxy. The carbon nano materials are mainly distributed in resin rich region of the composite laminates.

Table 2. Material codes of composite laminates for the evaluation of complex permittivity.

Carbon Black		Carbon Nanofiber	
Code	Weight content [wt%]	Code	Weight content [wt%]
CB010	1.0	CNF005	0.5
CB020	2.0	CNF010	1.0
CB030	3.0	CNF020	2.0
CB040	4.0	CNF025	2.5
CB050	5.0		

Figure 3. Carbon nano materials and the cross sectional configurations of the composite material containing 2wt% of carbon nano materials.

If the void content in the epoxy is negligible and the theoretical density of carbon nano materials ρ_{CNM} (ρ_{CNM} is assumed to be 2.0 g/cm^3) is much higher than $w\rho_{epoxy}$ (the density of epoxy ρ_{epoxy} is about 1.2 g/cm^3), the concentration p of carbon nano materials in the composite can be related to the weight content w in the epoxy resin as below,

$$p = \frac{v_r \rho_{epoxy}}{\rho_{CB} + w \rho_{epoxy}} w \approx \frac{v_r \rho_{epoxy}}{\rho_{CB}} w \quad (8)$$

Measurement of DC electric conductivity

A simple test method of measuring volume resistance values of square shaped samples was used to obtain the dc conductivity. The samples were precisely cut from composite laminates of 17 plies into squares of 25 mm and covered with the conductive silver paint on both opposite surfaces. The measurement device for the conductivity was HP3458A Digital Multi-meter. The device can measure the resistance in the range of $10\ \Omega - 1\ \text{G}\ \Omega$. Considering the shape of the specimens, the lower limit of the conductivity measurement was about $10^{-12}\ \text{S/cm}$. Figure 4 shows (a) the measurement setup and (b) the dc conductivity obtained from the experiment. The dc conductivity of E-glass fabric/epoxy composite laminate itself is below the limit of measuring. The order of increasing rates of the dc conductivities with respect to filler concentrations is $\text{CNF} > \text{CB}$. The percolation thresholds of the composite to get the solid lines of equation (1) are all assumed to be near zero [3, 4].

Figure 4. (a) Setup to measure DC electrical conductivity in through-the-thickness direction of nanocomposites. (b) DC conductivities of composite laminates. The solid lines are the cases that the percolation thresholds are all assumed to be near zero.

Measurement of DC electric conductivity

In order to measure the complex permittivity at the microwave frequency band, Agilent N5230A (PNA-L Vector Network Analyzer) and 7 mm coaxial airline with Agilent N3696A (Electrical Calibration Module) were used.

Figure 5. Setup to measure the complex permittivity and an image of the test specimen.

The specimens used for the complex permittivity measurements were machined out of composite plates, so that the specimen could be inserted into the coaxial airline. Figure 5 shows the system setup for complex permittivity measurement. The complex permittivity was obtained using Agilent 85071E (Material Measurement Software), in which the Nicolson–Ross–Weir method is implicated, from scattering parameters for reflected and transmitted TEM microwaves which were continuously measured from 0.5 GHz to 18 GHz.

VERIFICATION AND DISCUSSION

The critical weight contents w_c as percolation thresholds are all zero. Using the equation (8), we can get the equation (9) as below,

$$K_i \approx a_i w^{b_i} + c_i \quad (9)$$

Using the equation (9), the complex permittivity, ε_r can be defined as a function of w and f . The constants x , y , a_i , b_i , c_i and p_c can be obtained from the measured properties (Table 3). In this study, we obtained the exponents x , y to be 0.7, 0.3 for CB and 0.85, 0.15 for CNF. This difference of x , y between two carbon nano material is due to the difference of their configuration. That is, the fibrous shape of CNF is more beneficial to make larger cluster or infinite cluster (network) than the spherical shape of CB. This benefit of CNF brings the slow drop of the permittivity of the CNF nanocomposite in frequency domain.

Figure 6 and figure 7 shows the average values (symbolic points) of real and imaginary parts of complex permittivity obtained from the experiment and the simulated values (solid lines) from the numerical model respectively in linear-linear scale and log-log scale. In these figures, we can see that the simulation model well follows the measurements.

It was observed that, the complex permittivity of the CNF increases more rapidly than that of CB as the filler concentration increases. As compared to the real part, the imaginary part of the complex permittivity increases much more rapidly as the filler concentration increases.

CONCLUSION

- (a) Numerical model for complex permittivity of composite was proposed, which is applicable in the microwave frequency band of $p > p_c$ and $L(\omega) < \zeta$.
 - A. The equation shapes of the model are based on the percolation theory but the constants must be obtained from the specific material system and manufacturing procedure.
- (b) E-glass fabric/epoxy composite laminates containing CB, CNF was fabricated and the DC an AC electric properties were measured. The numerical models were built up for the two composites respectively.

- A. The exponents x , y for CB (0.7, 0.3) were much different from those of CNF (0.85, 0.15). This is due to the difference in their inherent configuration of each individual particle.
- B. The numerical model was verified by compared with the measurement in both linear-linear scale and log-log scale.
- C. The CNF is more beneficial to get higher complex permittivity than CB.
- D. The imaginary part of complex permittivity increases much more rapidly than the real part as the filler concentration increases.

Figure 6. Experiments and the numerical model for the complex permittivity in linear-linear scale.

Figure 7. Experiments and the numerical model for the complex permittivity in log-log scale.

Table 3. Parameters for the semi-empirical model of complex permittivity of CB and CNF composite laminates.

CB composite laminates; $x = 0.70$, $y = 0.30$			
	a_i	b_i	c_i
K_1	1.2183E-08	1.9650	2.5352E-08
K_2	1.1597E-03	5.2413	7.3237E-03
K_3	2.2995E+02	2.5837	9.7033E+02
K_4	-3.6532E-02	3.2883	4.4698E+00
CNF composite laminates; $x = 0.85$, $y = 0.15$			
	a_i	b_i	c_i
K_1	8.3483E-09	1.4887	3.2548E-09
K_2	2.7469E-01	3.1229	3.7050E-02
K_3	6.8715E+02	1.7207	2.6904E+02
K_4	-1.4572E+01	1.8592	-3.7830E-01

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